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A Comparative Study of the Composition and Physico-Mechanical Properties of Bricks from Different Periods

Armando Zagaroli^{a*}, Francesco Santoro De Vico^b, Encarnación Ruiz Agudo^b, Jan Kubica^a,
Carlos Rodriguez-Navarro^b, Marcin Górski^a

- a Department of Structural Engineering, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Silesian University of Technology, Gliwice, Poland
b Department of Mineralogía y Petrología, Universidad de Granada, Granada, Spain

Abstract:

A crucial issue connected with the actual conservation of old masonry elements is the compatibility of the new material applied to heritage structures. Knowledge of the physical, chemical and mineralogical properties of bricks represents a key point in this regard. In order to evaluate the fine internal structure of brick, an investigation of samples from three types of ceramic bricks has been carried out using both destructive and non-destructive techniques, such as X-ray powder diffraction, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy, Thermogravimetric analysis, and Scanning electron microscopy. An evaluation of internal damage and porosity distribution was also performed by means of micro-CT analyses. The bricks tested came from different historical periods: solid brick from the ruins of a medieval castle in the southern part of Poland ("hand-made" from the 14th century), solid clay brick from the turn of the 18th / 19th century and, for comparison, a new solid clay brick with a mean compressive strength not less than 15MPa. Our results show the variability of the main mineralogical and physical properties of the bricks from the reference periods analyzed, specifically the different ratios of quartz to feldspar and the decrease in mullite ($Al_6Si_2O_{13}$) and iron oxides content from the oldest to the newest material reflecting the amount of clay in the green body. Compressive tests on non-standardized cubic samples were performed, showing the highest values for the material coming from the 18th century. Reasons for such a behavior are principally related to the reduced level of porosity and the pore morphology and size distribution.

Keywords: Clay bricks, Mineralogical and Morphological Properties, Compressive Strength, Porosity

*Corresponding author email address: Armando.Zagaroli@polsl.pl

1 Introduction

The mechanical characterization of masonry materials is crucial for the maintenance and improvement of building performance against gravity and seismic loads. Such analysis is even more relevant in relation to the assessment of historical structures belonging to the built heritage. Knowledge of the compressive strength of the bricks, determined following the actual European code, EN 1996-1-1(2005), appears significant for structural safety. Indirect information on the compressive strength can be obtained using several techniques (e.g., Schmidt hammer, micro drilling, and ultrasonic pulse velocity test), and direct tests are usually performed on non-standardized specimens. The issue of the feasibility of such procedure is still open because several factors can influence the test results, including the confinement effects of the platens, the slenderness of the specimens, presence of defects, or the anisotropy in the response due to the manufacturing process. Furthermore, comparative studies with different brick shapes and ages are rare due to the restrictions for sampling material from historical structures (Matysek and Witkowski 2016).

Complementary to mechanical characterization, mineralogical, petrographic, and physical investigations can add valuable information regarding the production processes, imperfections, and actual state of the masonry. Within this context, chemical-physical characterization of ancient bricks has been recently carried out to find the most suitable replacement bricks compatible with the original material both at European level (Lourenço et al. 2010) and elsewhere (Mishra and Mishra 2021, Araújo et al. 2020, Han et al. 2022). While chemical and mineralogical analyses present limitations in giving information on the compressive strength of bricks (Dizhur et al. 2017), physical properties such as porosity are closely related to the material strength (Garbin et al. 2019, Ramos Gavilán et al. 2018).

Here, a complete investigation on samples taken from three types of solid ceramic bricks has been carried out using both destructive and non-destructive techniques for understanding their microscale properties. Mechanical tests on full bricks currently used in engineering practice and non-standardized cubic samples from different historical periods have been performed to determine their compressive strength. Analysis of the porosity, evaluated on cylindrical cores drilled from the different brick types, was performed to correlate brick pore features with the compressive strength of cubic samples and their mineralogical-chemical properties, with the future objective of a multiscale assessment of more complex masonry systems (Ergenç et al. 2022).

2 Tests methods

Brick samples come from different historical periods: (i) solid bricks from the ruins of a medieval castle in the southern part of Poland ("hand-made" from the 14th century), (ii) solid clay bricks from the turn of the 18th / 19th century and for comparison, (iii) new solid clay bricks with an average compressive strength not inferior to 15MPa. The abbreviations CB1, CB2 and CB3 are used to refer to the medieval (XIV c.), end of XVIII c., and contemporary (XXI c.) brick material, respectively. The subsequent letter -C and -F is related to the shape of the tested specimens, cubic or full unit, respectively (Table 1). The old bricks, from the 14th c. and from the turn of the 18th / 19th c., come from the ruins of a castle, originally built as a masonry structure in the 14th c., and located in the southern part of Poland, in the historical and geographical region (named in Latin as *Polonia Minor*). Until 1945, the castle was called Schloss Neudeck. Bricks from the 14th century come from the ruins of the underground, medieval part of the original body of the castle, while the bricks from the turn of the 18th/19th c. come from the remains of the ruins of the northern wing of the castle, built in this period. The original dimensions of medieval bricks from the Silesia area, according to the available data and information (Borusiewicz 1985) were usually as follows: length

258-263 mm; width 112-118 mm and height 84-93 mm. Bricks from the turn of the 18th/19th c. usually had significantly lower height. In Silesia and the neighboring Małopolska region, their dimensions were within the following limits: length 260-285 mm; width 120-125 mm and height 50-60 mm. Nominal dimensions of new tested bricks were $250 \times 120 \times 65$ mm.

The micro-scale properties were investigated experimentally with a complete characterization using the following analytical techniques. X-ray diffraction (XRD) was employed to identify the mineralogical composition of the bricks. A PANalytical X'Pert Pro X-ray diffractometer was used. The following conditions were applied: Cu K α radiation, $\lambda = 1.5405 \text{ \AA}$, 3° – 70° 2θ explored range, scanning rate of $0.11^\circ 2\theta \text{ s}^{-1}$). XRD patterns were interpreted using the HighScore Plus software package to obtain semiquantitative data using the RIR (reference intensity ratio) method. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was used to analyze the different phases present in the bricks. The ATRproONE-FTIR, Jasco Model 6600 was used with 400 – 4000 cm^{-1} frequency range, with resolution of 2 cm^{-1} , and 100 accumulations. The amount of carbonate phases was determined by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) using a Mettler Toledo TGA/DSC 3+ system in N $_2$ flow atmosphere at a T range of 20 – $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and at a controlled heating rate of $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. A Phenom XL G2 desktop scanning electron microscope (SEM) with a CeB $_6$ electron source and secondary and back-scattered electron detectors coupled with an energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDX) was used to collect high-resolution images and elemental maps of the bricks to obtain insights into the 2D structure of the matrix and the pore system. Petrographic thin sections were prepared for SEM and EDX analysis. X-ray micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) was performed on cylindrical samples (0.7 cm diameter and 1.2 cm height) using an Xradia Versa 510 (Zeiss) for the analysis of the 3D spatial distribution, structure, and quantification of empty spaces (pores) using high-resolution contrast images. Scans were performed at 40 kV and $5 \text{ }\mu\text{A}$. Data were acquired with a $4\times$ magnification CCD objective for a total scan time of 15 h including the collection of reference images. The voxel size achieved under these conditions was $3 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. It should be noted that micro-CT analyses were carried out on cylindrical samples obtained by drilling the same brick samples used for preparing thin sections. Prior to micro-CT analysis, the brick samples were analyzed with SEM-EDX to avoid any potential error in the selection of the gray-level/contrast threshold to quantify the selected phases/pores. The image analysis was performed using Dragonfly software (Version 4.1, Object Research Systems). With the use of this software, more than 3000 high-resolution images were merged, and then the void phase present in the sample was superimposed. A working mask was constructed from which the voxels that did not give signals in Z were detected, i.e., the empty voxels.

Regarding the macro scale properties, compressive tests on full bricks and cubic samples obtained from full units were performed. While for the new brick material a series consisting of 6 solid clay bricks ($250 \times 120 \times 65 \text{ mm}$) and 6 cubic samples ($40 \times 40 \times 40 \text{ mm}$) was considered, for the medieval and contemporary bricks, one series of 7 and 6 cubic samples was tested. The analyses were performed in displacement-control on full bricks with direction perpendicular to the bed face and load-control on cubic samples. Modifications in the test set-up allow to obtain information about the elastic modulus and the softening behavior other than the peak strength, the unique parameter collected with the test on cubic samples. Preparation of the surface and measuring of the samples according to EN 772-16 (2011) was carried out before the experimental observations in line with EN 772-1 (2011).

Table 1. Characteristics of the specimens tested in compression

Specimens	shape and dimensions [mm]	Weight (CoV) [g]	Remarks
CB1-C	Cubic 40 × 40 × 40	114.29 (0.03)	Cut from medieval hand-molded brick (XIV c.)
CB2-C	Cubic 40 × 40 × 40	104.83 (0.04)	Cut from hand-molded brick (XVIII c.)
CB3-C	Cubic 40 × 40 × 40	105.3 (0.03)	Cut from modern machine-molded brick
CB3-F	Full brick 250 × 120 × 65	2805.0 (0.02)	Modern machine-molded brick (strength class "15")

3 Results:

3.1 Mineralogical properties

The results of the XRD analysis are presented in Figure 1. The CB1 sample shows the presence of up to 13 wt% mullite, the highest content among all the brick specimens. No feldspars or calcite were found in this sample. The CB2 sample contains a lower amount of mullite (8 wt%) but includes feldspars (albite and microcline) in concentrations of 16 wt% and 12 wt%, respectively. The specimen CB3 contains a similar amount of mullite as the CB2 specimen, with a higher content of albite and microcline (26 wt% and 21 wt%, respectively). Minor amounts of magnesium and calcium silicates in the form of diopside and gehlenite were identified (minor than 2 wt%).

Figure 1. XRD analysis on the three studied bricks. (a) XRD patterns and (b) phase content determined from semi quantitative phase analysis using the RIR method (diopside and gehlenite marked with green and black points in the XRD patterns, respectively).

FTIR spectroscopy (Figure 2) confirmed the mineral composition previously determined by XRD analysis, providing additional valuable information regarding poorly crystalline and amorphous phases not detected using XRD. In particular, the presence of iron oxides can be inferred from the presence of vibration bands at 551, 469, 534, 424, 439 cm^{-1} , which correspond to hematite. The presence of silica/silicate phases (vibration bands at 1090–1050, 1160, 799–788, 699 and 530 cm^{-1}) was also evidenced. The presence of iron oxides can explain the reddish color of the material but this qualitative feature generally shows no clear correlation with the compressive strength (Almesfer et al. 2014).

Amorphous silica is the main component of the fired clay-matrix of the bricks and the observed bands are also present in crystalline silicates such as quartz and feldspars. Sample CB1 has a more intense broad quartz peak at 1048cm^{-1} , as compared with samples CB2 and CB3. This broad band between 1200cm^{-1} and 900cm^{-1} could be representative of not only some silicate phase (most likely quartz) but also a mixture of quartz plus silicate glass (brick matrix) and also other peaks resulting from the presence of calcium carbonate at 874cm^{-1} . Because of the absence of the peak at 714cm^{-1} , which corresponds to the asymmetric plane stretching vibration of O-C-O in carbonate groups of calcite, we can state that the presented small peaks in Figure 2 at 874cm^{-1} of calcium carbonate do not correspond to calcite. In addition, the absence of a band at $\sim 1400\text{cm}^{-1}$ (ν_3 of CO_3 groups) shows absence of carbonate phases in these samples. Altogether, the FTIR results are in good agreement with and complement the results of the XRD analysis.

Figure 2. FTIR spectra on the three bricks studied. The bands corresponding to quartz and hematite are indicated (black and brown points, respectively)

The TGA-DSC results clearly demonstrate the presence of trace amounts (3 wt%) of CaCO_3 in sample CB2, shown by the weight loss resulting from the decomposition of CaCO_3 into CaO at a temperature range of $680\text{--}780^\circ\text{C}$ (Figure 3). Such a small amount is below the detection limits of XRD and FTIR. The DSC plot does not show any distinctive feature other than a general broad endothermic band corresponding to the loss of water from the alumino-silicate matrix. Basically, the main difference among the three types of bricks (other than the small content of carbonate in CB2), is the slightly larger overall weight loss of sample CB1 in the T range $30\text{--}650^\circ\text{C}$, likely due to de-hydroxylation of the partially re-hydroxylated clay minerals in the brick matrix. The octahedral layers of clays have the vertices occupied by hydroxyl groups. During firing, OH groups are removed. Note that it has been experimentally shown that de-hydroxylated clays in ancient bricks re-hydroxylate over time, this process being extremely slow (Wilson et al. 2009). Therefore, older bricks show a larger degree of re-hydroxylation than younger ones, which is consistent with our TGA results.

Figure 3. TGA analysis on the three bricks studied.

3.2 Morphological and physical properties

SEM-EDS analysis was performed to obtain insights into the microstructure and chemical composition of the bricks. This analysis was complemented by the study of the 3D microstructure and porosity of the bricks using micro-CT (Vásárhelyi et al. 2020). The analysis of thin sections of the CB1 specimen by SEM-EDS shows the heterogeneity of the oldest bricks. In the lower part of Figure 4a, the material is more close-packed than in the rest of the thin section, where larger grains are surrounded by pores. In the CB2 sample (Figure 4d), it is observed a more compact texture with lower porosity. Furthermore, the shape of voids is circular and regular in contrast to the highly irregular and elongated pores seen in the previous sample. From a tridimensional point of view, these observations on the pore structure can be confirmed by micro-CT analysis. In sample CB1, there are many voids surrounding large grains (Figure 4b), compared with sample CB2 (Figure 4e) in which two behaviors are noted differently: there are areas where there is a lot of heterogeneity between matrix, consisting of smaller grains that are more closely packed together and among porosity. In other areas of the CB2 petrographic section you can see there are large crystals with significant voids around the grains. The matrix of modern bricks CB3 (Figure 4c) is even more compact, with higher amount of pores and a more homogeneous distribution of voids than the two older bricks, and large pores are not observed surrounding the largest particles. Total porosity values of 29.65%, 13.33% and 35.93% were determined for samples CB1, CB2 and CB3, respectively, using Dragonfly software with a spatial resolution of 70 nm voxel size (see “Tests methods” paragraph).

Figure 4. SEM (a, d) and micro-CT (b, c, e) images of the bricks studied. Elemental maps are also included in the secondary electron images obtained by SEM (a, d). (a) and (b) images correspond to sample CB1, (e) and (d) images correspond to sample CB2. Figure (c) corresponds to the CB3 sample. The yellow arrows show the interface between the large quartz grain and the matrix. Yellow areas in the micro-CT images show voids (i.e., pores). The bright-white spots correspond to phases with high Z value (e.g., iron oxides).

3.3 Mechanical properties

Analysis of the mechanical properties of masonry constituents is crucial for determining experimentally or numerically the properties of existing masonry structures (Jafari et al. 2022). Even though the tensional state of bricks results in a combination of compression and bi-axial tension, when the masonry is subjected to vertical loads, as it is usually the case of historical buildings with mortar softer than bricks (Hilsdorf 1969), the brick compressive strength is one of the input parameters for determining the stress-strain relationship of masonry (Kaushik et al. 2007). In the case of the modern material (Figure 5a), a ratio of 1.50 between the compressive strength of the full units and cubic samples was found. In terms of normalized compressive strength as recommended by EN 772-1 (2011) and assuming equal normalized compressive strengths for full bricks and cubic samples, it can be determined a value for the shape factor of the cubic samples of 1.14. This is in line with the mean shape factor of 1.16 that can be deduced from Cabané et al. (2022) in their recent analysis of 461 cubic ($40 \times 40 \times 40$ mm) and standard unit samples of $100 \times 100 \times 40$ mm. Assuming the value mentioned above, the compressive strength of the cubic samples and mean dimensions of the medieval and end of 18th c. bricks, a preliminary estimation of their strength can be also achieved, but which nevertheless has to be supported with further experimental or numerical analyses. In this case, for full brick units CB1 and CB2, compressive strength of 13.12 MPa and 64.03 MPa have been estimated. For cubic samples CB1, CB2 and CB3, compressive strengths of 10.64 MPa, 42.34 MPa and 27.15 MPa were reached, respectively (Figure 5b). As expected, the compressive strength of medieval specimens is very limited compared to the rest of the bricks.

Figure 5. Compressive strength results for full brick units and cubic samples made of modern material (a), compressive strength of cubes made of material from different historical periods (b).

4 Discussion

In this study, the mineralogical, chemical, and microstructural characterization of brick samples provided useful insights into the internal structure of such materials. The presence of mullite determined by XRD, which forms at high firing temperature (≥ 900 °C) (Cultrone et al., 2001), is thus somehow correlated to the degree of vitrification and densification, resulting in material with high compressive strength and low porosity (Sedmale et al. 2004). Generally, the increase in firing temperature is accompanied by a larger degree of vitrification especially for non-carbonate rich clays, leading to an overall increase in compressive strength (Elert et al. 2003). Furthermore, the use of feldspars as a fluxing agent in the brick raw materials has been positively correlated with an increase in the compressive strength (Kieufack et al. 2021). However, the presence of microcline and albite, used during brick manufacturing to improve the technological process, is not accompanied by a corresponding increase in the compressive strength of the materials analyzed here.

FTIR analyses were helpful in identifying that no additives were used and that iron oxides were present, also detected by XRD. TGA results show different thermal events related to phyllosilicate de-hydroxylation and decomposition of calcite reflecting the CO_2 lost during decarbonation. Wilson et al. (2009) showed that long-time calcined bricks, in contact with the environment, begin to rehydrate. The process of rehydroxylation is so slow that a complete rehydration does not occur. Thus, the study of the degree of rehydration provides information regarding the age of the fired brick. Our results are in line with this study, since the oldest sample tested here (CB1) has had more rehydration, and therefore it loses more water during TGA. This effect, however, could not be correlated with the observed differences in compressive strength among the tested bricks. This is likely because of the diversity in the industrial production and composition of the materials used during different ages. However, quartz was used as the principal inert in southern Poland in the 14th c. compared to the bricks used in the same region later on (end of 18th c.) and in the present. Regarding the results of micro-CT analyses, the brick from the 18th/19th c. (CB2) is showing the lowest value of porosity and also a pronounced detachment between quartz grains and the matrix, that could contribute to a better mechanical behavior. This is reflected in the mechanical tests, showing the highest compressive strength for the CB2-C samples, with a mean compressive strength value $>35\%$ higher than that of the cubes from the modern bricks. Sample CB1 shows a highly heterogeneous internal structure with abundant pores surrounding the larger grains, in contrast to sample CB3 which has a more homogeneous structure. In addition, even though CB3 is the sample with the highest porosity, it bears compressive loads better than the 14th c. sample (Figure 6). This contrasting behavior could arise from the differences in grain

sizes, with smaller grains used nowadays in industry, which markedly change the structure of the sample overall. Pore shape is controlled by the geometry and packing of the mineral grains. Large pores are associated with the larger grains, creating preferential anisotropy fracture planes in the sample as compared to the greater compactness in the grain boundaries of the modern sample. This is clearly observed in the 14th c. sample (Figure 4a-b), where detachment of large grains can be seen and this is why large, elongated pores developed.

Figure 6. Compressive strength and porosity trends were analyzed.

5 Conclusions

Based on the results of the bricks characterization carried out, it is possible to conclude that:

- The chemical/mineralogical analyses of the bricks from different periods of time are crucial to understanding the difference in the performance of building materials and firing technology.
- X-ray microtomography and scanning electron microscopy analyses contributed to the microstructural characterization of the samples, deepening into our understanding of the relation between compressive strength and physical properties, specifically revealing how pore volume and shape, which are largely controlled by the geometry and packing of the minerals, influence the mechanical behavior of the bricks.
- Through mechanical tests on non-standard cubic samples, it was found that the 18th century samples have the highest compressive strength and, although the oldest brick material is more porous than the newest, the latter preserves a greater resistance. These results could be related with the different mineralogical composition and the location/shape of the pores within the samples related to the mineralogy of the raw (green) materials and the firing conditions.

Future studies will deal with characterization of binders of different ages that allow a comparative multiscale assessment of bigger masonry assemblages and retrofit systems.

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